

Diffusion characteristics of solvent toluene into nano calcium carbonate filled natural rubber composites

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Abstract : Solvent absorptions were studied in vulcanized rubber samples of widely varying amounts of nano calcium carbonate with a view to rate-limiting steps, the major diffusion rate control and other solvent properties. The surface resistance (the mass flux through the polymer surface, F_s) was found to affect the absorption process of the composites. The sorption results were interpreted by using first-order kinetic model. The S-shaped curvature clearly indicates that solvent uptake process is significantly control by surface resistance in the present experiment. The h_{ap} (the surface mass transfer coefficient) values for all the nano composite samples are always higher than the corresponding gum values. This indicates that time required for solvent molecules to get place on the composite sample surface is prominent. The B (the ratio of diffusional resistance and surface resistance) values ranging from 9 to 55, are not very high (i.e. <100), hence the surface resistance is important. The D_c (diffusion coefficient corrected for free film exposed on two sides) value increases with filler loading. The comparable E_D (the activation energy of diffusion) values of gum and composites, expect good elastic properties in composites. The values of n (an idea about the mechanism of solvent transport) obtained for the different nano composites show anomalous ($0.5 < n < 1.0$) behaviour.

Keywords : Nano calcium carbonate, natural rubber, solvent transport, diffusion coefficient, permeation coefficient, heats of sorption, mass transfer coefficients.

Introduction

Rubbers are filled with filler usually for improving properties (reinforcement). Filler technology can be taken into account a variety of rubber composite technology from nano to micron level. For gas adsorption, certain fillers for example carbon black shows surface morphology is more important than experimental temperature and pressure¹⁻³. The transport of organic liquids through rubber composites is of industrial significance in a multiplicity of appliances⁴ such as food packaging, pervaporation⁵, control drug release and pesticides, electrodialysis⁶ etc. Literature reports on the diffusion and sorption processes in carbon black and silica loaded natural rubber and its blends with other polymers⁷⁻¹¹. At a very low filler loading, nano filler rubber composites have created a center of attention throughout the scientific community^{12,13}. According to the anisometry (breadth/length, ratio), the nature of the nano fillers varies. Moreover presence of high specific component of surface energy, nano filler has a tendency to agglomer-

ate. In many cases, modification of nano filler is a must. Nano fillers have a significant influence on the sorption property and permeability to diffusants of an elastomer. There are some studies carried out on rubber nanocomposites using nano carbon black and silica fillers in natural rubber¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Nano calcium carbonate is an important filler in rubber because of its good balance of properties and it has become a very contesting filler for the automobile rubber products and other specialized products. Therefore, nano calcium carbonate was selected for this study.

The principal aim of the present work is to investigate the effect of nano size calcium carbonate on the phenomenon of diffusion of aromatic hydrocarbon (toluene) through the vulcanized natural rubber composites. Diffusion process was carried out at 28, 50 and 70 °C. The effects of filler loading, temperature and thickness of the sample on the sorption behavior have been investigated. The object of this study is also to evaluate the kinetics of the trans-

Table 1. Composition of rubber chips (Basic recipe of the mix samples)

Ingredient	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇
Natural rubber (RMA-IX)	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Zinc oxide	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5
Stearic acid	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
IPPD ^a	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Sulfur	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
BSM ^b	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
Nano CaCO ₃	-	5.0	10.0	15.0	20.0	25.0	30.0	35.0

^aIsopropyl parphenylenediamine.

^bN-Oxydiethyl benzthiazyl sulfonamide.

port phenomenon with a discussion on the usefulness of transport coefficients in rubber nano composite systems.

Results and discussion

The samples of rubber chips in eight different formulas are presented in Table 1.

The swelling of the chip at any time is reported in terms of percentage of the moles of solvent uptake by 100 g of sample, Q_t is mol%, which can be calculated using the following eq. (1) :

$$Q_t (\text{mol}\%) = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{Mass of the solvent sorbed}}{\text{Molar mass of solvent}} \right)}{\text{Initial mass of the chip (g)}} \times 100 (\text{g}) \quad (1)$$

The equilibrium value for solvent uptake is related to the amount of polymer only in the sample. Therefore, the equilibrium value for solvent uptake is calculated assuming that the filler does not swell. The sorption data, expressed as mol% uptake of the solvent toluene and square root of time, $t^{1/2}$ have been calculated from the experiment conducted at three different sample thickness (0.15, 0.075 and 0.035 cm) and at three different temperatures (28, 50 and 70 °C). Figs. 1 and 2 shows the toluene uptake of gum and nano calcium carbonate filler loaded samples of 0.035 cm thickness at 28 °C. It is clearly evident that gum samples possesses higher solvent take-up than the loaded sample. Among the loaded samples, the solvent uptake decreases with increasing filler loading amount at a particular temperature. The S-shaped curvatures were also observed for all the experimental samples at three different temperatures and for thickness variation. This clearly indicates that solvent uptake pro-

Fig. 1. Mol% toluene up-take of gum (without filler sample) and nano calcium carbonate loaded vulcanized samples having 0.035 cm thickness at 28 °C.

cess is completely control by surface resistance in the present experiment. The values of equilibrium solvent take-up (Q_{∞}) of the composites are given in Table 2. The equilibrium solvent take-up (Q_{∞}) decreases with increasing amount of filler in the sample. This is due to the decrease of mean free path within the rubber-filler network.

Surface mass transfer coefficients and transport coefficients :

In S-shape type solvent absorption, solvent advancing into a rubber composite is initially slow. The process

Fig. 2. Initial portion of mol% toluene up-take of gum (without filler sample) and nano calcium carbonate loaded vulcanized samples having 0.035 cm thickness at 28 °C.

continues until the solvent concentration is sufficiently high. At equilibrium, the mass flux through the polymer surface (F_s) can express by the eq. (2) :

$$-D (dC/dx) = h (C_\infty - C_s) = F_s \quad (2)$$

C_∞ and C_s (the boundary condition at the surface for absorption) are the concentrations in the sample at equilibrium and in the surface, D is the diffusion coefficient (cm^2/s), h is the surface mass transfer coefficient (cm/s) and C is the concentrations (g/cm^3). Hence the unit of F_s will be $\text{g}/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ s})$. For generalized solution to the diffu-

sion eq. (2), a dimensionless time parameter, T , is used as

$$T = Dt/L^2 \quad (3)$$

A useful dimensionless surface condition parameter (B) that varies from ∞ to 0.1 gives the ratio of resistance to transport from diffusion in the sample (R_d) to the resistance associated with the surface condition (R_s). Thus

$$B = \frac{R_d}{R_s} = \frac{L/D}{1/h} = \frac{\text{Diffusional resistance}}{\text{Surface resistance}} \quad (4)$$

where, L is the thickness in cm of the free sample exposed on two sides. The process of estimation for h is the slope of a plot F versus time extrapolated to zero time from an initial concentration that need not be zero,

$$h = [F/(C_\infty - C_s)]_{t=0} \quad (5)$$

The diffusion coefficient (D) is calculated from time required for half of the dimensionless time parameter ($T_{1/2}$) to the diffusion eq. (3) :

$$T_{1/2} = Dt_{1/2}/L^2 = 0.049$$

or

$$D = \frac{0.049 \times L^2}{t_{1/2}} \quad (6)$$

The constant 0.049 comes from the solution of the diffusion equation for a constant diffusion coefficient and having no surface resistance. If there is a significant surface resistance, an apparent diffusion coefficient (D_s) is found using the measured half time of absorption, i.e. in this situation,

Table 2. Values of equilibrium sorption (Q_∞) (mol% toluene)

Thickness (cm)	Temp. (°C)	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇
0.035 (Low)	28	3.996	3.654	3.218	2.971	2.831	2.479	2.546	2.341
	50	3.505	3.350	2.860	2.904	2.510	2.417	2.526	2.293
	70	3.423	2.942	2.946	2.743	2.433	2.474	2.442	2.177
0.075 (Medium)	28	4.035	3.521	3.297	3.080	2.817	2.631	2.652	2.403
	50	3.729	3.307	3.116	2.921	2.709	2.588	2.570	2.302
0.150 (High)	70	3.450	2.906	2.868	2.804	2.637	2.401	2.486	2.270
	28	3.520	3.405	3.031	3.020	2.806	2.726	2.705	2.395
	50	3.671	3.209	2.929	2.01	2.725	2.655	2.523	2.229
	70	3.521	3.012	2.895	2.872	2.576	2.548	2.564	2.162

$$D_a = \frac{0.049 \times L^2}{t_{1/2}} \quad (7)$$

Corrections are applied to this eq. (7) if there is significant diffusion (related to thickness) from the sides of samples. For this purpose apparent diffusion coefficient (D_a) is corrected in isotropic media¹⁷ :

$$D_c = \frac{D_a}{\left(1 + \frac{L}{l} + \frac{L}{w}\right)^2} \quad (8)$$

where length and width of the sample are l and w respectively and L is its thickness.

The important sorption properties for gum and seven

nano calcium carbonate-natural rubber composites are presented in Tables 3–5 using toluene at 28, 50 and 70 °C. All the systems studied here have reached equilibrium, so mass flux of toluene through each of the composite surface at equilibrium (F_∞) is given.

If the value of h_{app} is high, then it is obvious that time required for solvent molecules to get place on the sample surface is prominent. For all the nano composite samples their h_{app} values are higher than the corresponding gum values at all thickness levels and also at various temperatures. For a particular thickness, the h_{app} values increases with the increase in experimental temperature.

The useful dimensionless quantity (B) in eq. (4), indicates the process mechanism during sorption. A large B -

Table 3. Results of absorption experiments for nano CaCO₃-NR composites at 28 °C

Thickness (cm)	Parameter	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇
0.035	F_∞ (g/cm ² s)	0.156	0.147	0.147	0.147	0.145	0.103	0.097	0.096
	h_{app} (cm/s) × 10 ⁴	1.04	1.29	1.29	1.29	1.32	1.80	1.93	1.93
	B	14	15	14	14	13	12	10	09
	D_c (cm ² /s) × 10 ⁷	2.56	2.89	2.91	3.60	3.62	5.04	5.38	5.93
0.075	F_∞ (g/cm ² s)	0.354	0.255	0.252	0.248	0.241	0.244	0.211	0.211
	h_{app} (cm/s) × 10 ⁴	1.09	1.56	1.53	1.55	1.59	1.53	1.77	1.77
	B	27	25	23	24	26	23	23	19
	D_c (cm ² /s) × 10 ⁷	3.02	4.33	4.51	4.52	4.52	4.52	5.75	5.98
0.150	F_∞ (g/cm ² s)	0.557	0.499	0.465	0.490	0.463	0.458	0.456	0.418
	h_{app} (cm/s) × 10 ⁴	1.12	1.31	1.66	1.68	1.64	1.80	1.82	1.94
	B	55	59	62	59	63	70	90	91
	D_c (cm ² /s) × 10 ⁷	3.10	3.29	3.48	3.74	3.87	3.86	4.05	4.08

Table 4. Results of absorption experiments for nano CaCO₃-NR composites at 50 °C

Thickness (cm)	Parameter	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇
0.035	F_∞ (g/cm ² s)	0.124	0.117	0.115	0.115	0.110	0.102	0.096	0.093
	h_{app} (cm/s) × 10 ⁴	1.23	1.58	1.57	1.57	1.82	2.25	2.23	2.23
	B	14	10	13	12	11	11	11	10
	D_c (cm ² /s) × 10 ⁷	5.57	5.62	5.64	5.81	5.84	6.87	6.98	6.99
0.075	F_∞ (g/cm ² s)	0.296	0.283	0.259	0.251	0.233	0.239	0.200	0.187
	h_{app} (cm/s) × 10 ⁴	1.86	1.93	1.98	2.09	2.06	2.12	2.33	2.77
	B	24	21	17	19	19	19	20	16
	D_c (cm ² /s) × 10 ⁷	5.74	8.16	8.13	8.13	8.36	8.44	8.51	8.52
0.150	F_∞ (g/cm ² s)	0.528	0.504	0.420	0.454	0.442	0.424	0.400	0.357
	h_{app} (cm/s) × 10 ⁴	2.01	1.74	1.94	2.31	2.21	1.99	2.32	2.50
	B	49	41	49	43	57	38	44	49
	D_c (cm ² /s) × 10 ⁷	6.18	6.34	7.61	7.66	7.74	7.82	7.92	8.43

value is for diffusion-controlled process which points out that equilibrium solvent concentration in the polymer will be reached after some reasonable time. For $B = 1$, diffusion resistance is equal to surface resistance. For B -values < 1 , surface resistance dominates. In the present experiment, all the B values at different thickness and at various temperatures are ranging from 9 to 55. As the B -values are not very high (i.e. < 100), the surface resistance is important.

The values of the diffusion coefficient (D_c) (given in Tables 3–5) can be calculated from the eq. (8). The values show that the variation of the diffusion coefficient also depends on the temperature, the filler amount and thickness of the sample¹⁸. The results indicate good distribution of nano particles in the rubber matrix. The diffusion coefficient (D_c) was observed increase with increases in sorption temperature. As the temperature increases, the amplitude of segmental oscillation of polymer chains also increases. Greater segmental motion results in an increase in the size of free volume. The present

experimental D_c values of the nano composites are in good agreement with the fact that diffusion rate of a solvent molecule through polymer is related mainly to the exchange capacity of the polymer chain segments regarding their positions with penetrant molecule, and the mobility of the polymer depends on the free volume available in the matrix¹⁹. At all temperatures and for all the thicknesses, the order in the values of D_c is $S_0 < S_1 < S_2 < S_3 < S_4 < S_5 < S_6 < S_7$ composite.

Activation parameters :

The temperature dependence of diffusion property was used to evaluate the activation energy for the diffusion process using the Arrhenius type relation²⁰.

$$\ln D_c = \ln D_0 - (E_D/RT) \tag{9}$$

where D_c represents diffusivity coefficient and D_0 is a constant. Plot of $\ln D_c$ against $1/T$ was used to calculate the activation energy of diffusion (E_D). Values of E_D and D_0 are tabulated in Table 6. The activation energy E_D does not show any systematic trend with the increase of

Table 5. Results of absorption experiments for nano CaCO₃-NR composites at 70 °C

Thickness (cm)	Parameter	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇
0.035	F_∞ (g/cm ² s)	0.125	0.133	0.130	0.107	0.120	0.095	0.085	0.087
	h_{app} (cm/s) $\times 10^4$	2.26	2.11	2.12	2.25	2.04	2.41	2.52	2.38
	B	13	12	09	12	09	10	10	09
	D_c (cm ² /s) $\times 10^7$	5.85	5.90	6.35	7.00	7.84	8.60	8.62	8.72
0.075	F_∞ (g/cm ² s)	0.307	0.250	0.230	0.202	0.207	0.222	0.212	0.191
	h_{app} (cm/s) $\times 10^4$	2.01	2.10	2.16	2.20	2.24	2.10	2.14	2.32
	B	25	19	19	21	20	21	18	18
	D_c (cm ² /s) $\times 10^7$	6.08	8.10	8.54	8.56	8.55	8.60	9.02	9.32
0.150	F_∞ (g/cm ² s)	0.478	0.453	0.445	0.440	0.434	0.399	0.389	0.351
	h_{app} (cm/s) $\times 10^4$	2.08	2.18	2.21	2.25	2.31	2.32	2.35	2.40
	B	43	44	45	45	46	42	42	42
	D_c (cm ² /s) $\times 10^7$	7.31	7.39	7.52	7.56	7.72	8.08	8.23	8.50

Table 6. Action parameters of nano CaCO₃-NR composites in toluene

Thickness (cm)	Parameter	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇
0.035	D_0 (cm ² /s)	0.125	0.166	0.143	0.193	0.150	0.271	0.489	0.394
	E_D (kJ/mol)	16.27	17.92	16.91	18.57	16.94	20.10	23.66	22.37
0.075	D_0 (cm ² /s)	0.173	0.198	0.222	0.230	0.201	0.285	0.322	0.334
	E_D (kJ/mol)	18.10	18.56	18.91	19.11	18.28	20.80	20.96	21.20
0.150	D_0 (cm ² /s)	0.121	0.133	0.143	0.167	0.185	0.155	0.168	0.160
	E_D (kJ/mol)	15.74	16.25	16.53	17.40	18.20	16.90	17.32	17.00

nano filler loading in composites. The activation energies of nano calcium carbonate rubber composites lie a little higher than gum values at thickness range of 0.035 to 0.150 cm, clearly indicated the flexible nature of the composites and it directly indicated that the glass transition temperature must be very low than compare to the room temperature. Hence the composites are expected good elastic properties²¹.

Transport mechanism :

With the aim of working out the mechanism of transport phenomenon of toluene through nano CaCO₃-NR composites, the sorption data have been fitted on to the relation²².

$$\ln\left(\frac{Q_t}{Q_\infty}\right) = \ln k + n \ln t \quad (10)$$

where Q_t and Q_∞ are respectively the moles % of solvent take-up at time t and at equilibrium, k is a constant which depends upon the structural peculiarities (in case of polymer composite, it is morphology) of the system and its

interaction with solvent. The value of n gives an idea about the mechanism of solvent transport. The values of n and k were obtained from the plot of $\ln(Q_t/Q_\infty)$ against $\ln t$ and are shown in Table 7. The initial portion of the plots (< 40% of the equilibrium toluene take-up) were used.

The value of n gives an idea about the mechanism of solvent transport. When $n = 0.5$ (it is called Fickian transport), the rate of diffusion of permeant molecules is much less than the polymer segment mobility. It is also called case I transport mechanism. When $n = 1.0$ (it is called non-Fickian transport), the rate of diffusion of permeant molecules is much greater than the polymer segment mobility. It is called case II transport mechanism. When $0.5 < n < 1.0$, it is called anomalous transport, the rate of diffusion of permeant molecules being nearer/similar to the polymer segment relaxation rate. When $n > 1$, the mode of transport is called super case II²³. Table 7 shows that the values of n obtained for the different nano composites at different temperatures and

Table 7. Transport parameters of nano CaCO₃-NR composites in toluene

Thickness Temperature	Parameter	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇
0.035 (cm)									
28 °C	$k \times 10^2$	1.82	1.63	1.59	1.25	1.52	1.52	1.50	1.92
	n	0.61	0.66	0.66	0.82	0.68	0.75	0.83	0.72
50 °C	$k \times 10^2$	2.62	1.38	1.59	1.58	1.30	2.24	2.24	1.94
	n	0.68	0.75	0.78	0.76	0.79	0.62	0.72	0.73
70 °C	$k \times 10^2$	3.15	2.70	2.91	2.90	2.90	2.91	2.57	2.95
	n	0.65	0.66	0.62	0.63	0.56	0.56	0.62	0.61
0.075 (cm)									
28 °C	$k \times 10^2$	1.08	0.98	1.04	0.81	0.81	0.92	0.89	0.58
	n	0.66	0.68	0.63	0.69	0.68	0.68	0.69	0.68
50 °C	$k \times 10^2$	1.35	1.17	0.35	1.03	1.55	1.05	1.03	1.13
	n	0.88	0.71	0.88	0.68	0.62	0.70	0.67	0.58
70 °C	$k \times 10^2$	2.00	1.05	1.91	2.17	1.55	1.27	1.02	1.28
	n	0.68	0.80	0.60	0.56	0.65	0.65	0.71	0.68
0.150 (cm)									
28 °C	$k \times 10^2$	0.67	0.60	0.49	0.88	0.59	0.62	0.75	0.61
	n	0.59	0.80	0.62	0.54	0.61	0.61	0.59	0.65
50 °C	$k \times 10^2$	0.79	0.88	0.83	0.95	0.95	0.91	0.97	1.08
	n	0.61	0.60	0.62	0.59	0.68	0.63	0.59	0.56
70 °C	$k \times 10^2$	0.78	0.63	0.80	0.93	0.75	1.07	0.82	0.68
	n	0.64	0.66	0.62	0.60	0.63	0.58	0.64	0.62

samples at different thicknesses are anomalous ($0.5 < n < 1.0$). The value of the constant k is characteristics of the system and an indication of the degree of filler rubber interaction. Table 7 shows with some exception of the higher thickness (0.15 cm), the k value for gum (S_0) compound shows highest value. The structure of filler-loaded composites poses lower mobility due to some hindrance and thus causes less volume expansion during solvent uptake process.

Experimental

Materials mixing techniques : All components were mixed together step by step in a two-roll mixing mill ($150 \times 300 \text{ mm}^2$) with a nip gap of 1.3 mm and a friction ratio 1 : 1 : 4 at initial temperature of 60 °C. Cured sheets of different thickness were prepared by curing in a compression mould using various dices. The predetermined time was allowed to cure the rubber sheet in a hydraulic press having electrically heated platens under a pressure of 45 kg/m². The sheets were cut into pieces of approximately of $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ size. All eight types of chips with different formulae were dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂ at room temperature for about 24 h. The chips were tested in the following experiments.

The solvent used was reagent grade toluene. Original weight and thickness of the samples were noted before sorption experiments. The solvent (15–20 ml) was filled in glass bottles having glass stoppers. The chips were then immersed in the solvent, and the stoppered bottles were kept in constant temperature bath and left to swell. The chips were then taken out at different time intervals; adhering liquid was removed by using filter paper and then weighed. The process was continued until equilibrium swelling (maximum swelling when the weight of the chip changed no more) was achieved. The experiments were done in triplicate and the results averaged. In order to study the effect of temperature on the sorption properties, the experiments were carried out at 28° (room temperature), 50° and 70 °C.

Conclusion

The results of the present experiment reveal that surface resistance to absorption is significant for nano

calcium carbonate-rubber composites. The low B values for all composites indicate delayed up-take of the solvent. The mechanism of transport is found to be anomalous mode at all thicknesses of the samples and the experimental temperatures. Good elastic properties of the nano-composites are assumed as because the E_D values of gum and composites are almost similar.

References

1. A. Schröder, M. Klüppel, R. H. Schuster and J. Heidberg, *Kautch. Gummi Kunstst.*, 2001, **54**, 260.
2. M. Klüppel, *Adv. Polym. Sci.*, 2003, **1**, 164.
3. G. Heinrich and M. Klüppel, *Kautch. Gummi Kunstst.*, 2001, **54**, 159.
4. T. D. Naylor, "Comprehensive Polymer Science", Pergamon Press, New York, 1989.
5. A. P. Mathew, S. Pakirisamy, M. G. Kumaran and S. Thomas, *Polymer*, 1995, **36**, 4935.
6. W. R. Vieth, "Diffusion in and through Polymers : Principles and Applications", Oxford University Press, New York, 1991.
7. A. Sujith, G. Unnikrishnan, C. K. Radhakrishnan and M. Padmini, *Polym. Compo.*, 2007, **5**, 705.
8. H. Ismile, B. T. Poh, K. S. Tan and M. Moorthy, *Polym. Int.*, 2003, **52**, 685.
9. H. C. Obasr, O. Ogbobe and I. O. Igwe, *Inter. J. Polym. Sci.*, Article, 2009, ID140682, 1.
10. G. Unnikrishnan and S. Thomas, *Polymer*, 1998, **39**, 3933.
11. P. Danwanichakul, S. Joroenkarn, P. J. Uumpathi and D. Dectojarassri Songklanakarin, *J. Sci. Technol.*, 2006, **28**, 1071.
12. D. Shach, G. Fytas and D. Vlassopolelos, *Langmuir*, 2005, **21**, 19.
13. H. C. Koh, J. S. Park, M. A. Jeong, H. Y. Hwang, H. T. Hong, S. Y. Ha and S. Y. Num, *Desalination*, 2008, **233**, 201.
14. L. Bokobza and O. Rapoport, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2002, **85**, 2301.
15. H. Ismail, B. T. Pho, K. S. Tan and M. Moorthy, *Polym. Int.*, 2003, **52**, 685.
16. R. Stephen, S. Varghese, K. Joseph, Z. Oommen and S. Thomas, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 2006, **282**, 162.
17. G. Marom, "The role of water transport in composite materials, in Polymer Permeability", ed. J. Comyn, Elsevier, London, 1985.
18. S. B. Harogopad and T. M. Aminabhavi, *Macromolecules*, 1991, **24**, 2598.

19. A. E. Mathai, R. P. Singh and S. Thomas, *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, 2003, **43**, 704.
20. A. E. Mathai and S. Thomas, *J. Macromol. Sci. Phys.*, 1996, **35**, 229.
21. S. B. Harogopad and T. M. Aminabhavi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 209.
22. L. M. Lutch and N. A. Peppas, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1987, **33**, 1557.
23. W. R. Vieth, "Diffusion in and through Polymers", Oxford University Press, New York, 1991.